

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Rab13 (UniProt ID: P51153) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

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Abstract

The small GTPase Rab13 is an important regulator of trans-Golgi to plasma membrane transport. *RAB13* upregulation is observed in cancer, and the functional roles of this protein remain to be determined. Here we have characterized eleven Rab13 commercial antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in *Rab13* knockout or knockdown cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

P51153, *RAB13*, Rab13, Ras-related protein Rab-13, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

Rab13 is a member of the Rab GTPase protein family, known for regulating membrane trafficking. It plays a role in vesicle trafficking between the trans-Golgi network and recycled endosomes (1). In addition to its function in vesicles transport, Rab13 regulates tight junction between epithelial cells (2). *RAB13* is upregulated in several cancers (3-5), and the protein is known to promote cell migration and cancer progression (6).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (7). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein (7). Here we characterized eleven commercial Rab13 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Rab13 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (8) and in Table 3 of this data note (7).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines (9). Rab13 is expressed at relatively high levels across most of the hundreds of cell lines analyzed by the DepMap organization (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) organization (10). A HEK-293T *RAB13* KO cell line available from Abcam was first used to screen eight Rab13 antibodies in western blot (Figure 1). WT and *RAB13* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with the eight Rab13 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1). Specific Rab13 antibodies were identified.

HEK293T are not suitable for testing antibodies in immunofluorescence due to their small size and clumping behavior. Using a specific Rab13 antibody identified in Figure 1, we evaluated Rab13 protein expression in cell lines chosen for their suitability in immunofluorescence testing, specifically large, flat, adherent cells, with the property of being transfectable with siRNA for mRNA knockdown (KD) (11, 12). We examined the DepMap transcriptomics database to identify cell lines that express Rab13 at levels greater than 2.5 log₂ (transcripts per million “TPM” + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (13) and selected 12 cell lines with RNA expression higher than 5.5 log₂ (TPM + 1) (Figure 2A). The cell lines selected are listed in

Table 1. The cell line U-87 MG, which expresses the *RAB13* transcript at 8.3 log₂ (TPM+1), presents the highest protein levels and was selected for downstream antibody screening.

A non-targeting control siRNA pool was used to treat U-87 MG control (ctrl) cells, while *RAB13* was KD using a pool of siRNA targeting this gene. A total of eleven antibodies were tested in western blot using ctrl and *RAB13* KD protein lysates to validate the efficiency of the siRNA treatment in reducing the Rab13 protein levels, and further evaluating antibody specificity in second cell line background (Figure 2B).

We then assessed the capability of the eleven antibodies to capture Rab13 from U-87 MG protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific Rab13 antibody identified in Figure 3 was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 3).

For immunofluorescence, all eleven antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, U-87 MG ctrl and *RAB13* KD cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the Rab13 antibodies were evaluated. Both ctrl and KD lines imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 4). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of ctrl and KD cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 5 are representative of this analysis (7).

In conclusion, we have screened eleven Rab13 commercial antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using genetic approaches. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (13). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect Rab13 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study Rab13 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Rab13 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. Moreover, the same antibody clones are donated by 2 manufacturers (cross-licensed antibodies, such as the 7G8A4 clone), effectively serving as replicates and enabling the validation of test reproducibility. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (7). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (14, 15). To knockdown *RAB13*, U-87 MG cells were treated with the *RAB13* SMARTPool from Horizon Discovery (cat. number L-008389-00-0005) for five days. U-87 MG control cells were treated with the ON-TARGETplus Non-targeting Control Pool (Horizon Discovery (cat. number. D-001810-10). Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 13778030) was used to transfect the siRNA following the manufacturer's protocol.

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21429 and A-21424). Peroxidase-conjugated Protein A for IP detection is from Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291.

Antibody screening by western blot

U-87 MG ctrl and *RAB13* KD cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at

room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

U-87 MG WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 $\times g$ for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels. Protein A:HRP was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.5 µg/ml.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

U-87 MG ctrl and *RAB13* KD cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. Ctrl and KD cells were plated on a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary Rab13 antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 \times 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 \times 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 \times 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices.

Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (16). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank -GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab255449	CVCL_0063	HEK-293T	WT
Abcam	ab266843	CVCL_B3FI	HEK-293T	<i>RAB13</i> KO
ATCC	CRL-2062	CVCL_1177	DMS 53	WT
ATCC	CCL-247	CVCL_0291	HCT 116	WT
ATCC	HTB-122	CVCL_1092	BT-549	WT
ATCC	CRL-1555	CVCL_0037	A-431	WT
ATCC	HTB-96	CVCL_0042	U-2 OS	WT
ATCC	HTB-14	CVCL_0022	U-87 MG	WT
ATCC	CCL-121	CVCL_0317	HT-1080	WT
ATCC	CRL-1469	CVCL_0480	PANC-1	WT
ATCC	HTB-9	CVCL_0126	5637	WT
ATCC	HTB-26	CVCL_0062	MDA-MB231	WT
ATCC	CCL-185	CVCL_0023	A549	WT
ATCC	CCL-2	CVCL_0030	HeLa	WT

Table 2: Summary of the Rab13 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab180936**	GR3449805-1	NA	recombinant mono	EPR14109(B)	rabbit	0.59	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab205528**	GR266687-2	NA	recombinant mono	EPR14110(2)	rabbit	1.06	Wb
Abcam	ab233810*	GR3247917-10	NA	monoclonal	7G8A4	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF, Flow Cyt
ABclonal	A10571	0056400201	AB_2758113	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.02	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB8305*	CIQP0122011	AB_3094838	monoclonal	863028	mouse	0.50	Wb
Proteintech	11718-1-AP	00142470	AB_3669132	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.55	Wb, IF
Proteintech	83336-2-RR**	23008225	AB_3670998	recombinant mono	240216D10	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-31878*	YA3806195	AB_2787501	monoclonal	8E8E2	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF, Flow Cyt
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-31879*	YA3806196	AB_2787502	monoclonal	7G8A4	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF, Flow Cyt
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-37779*	ZJ4493342	AB_2897703	monoclonal	1600CT724.2.34	mouse	0.50	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-52039	YA3805902A	AB_2646217	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF=immunofluorescence, Flow Cyt=flow cytometry.

**= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available.

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	WT/KO cell mosaic	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody
WT KO	WT KO	WT KO	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	WT	WT	WT
WT	WT	WT	SM	SM	SM	KO	KO	KO
KO	KO	KO	UB	UB	UB			
IP	IP	IP	IP	IP	IP			
kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa			
245-	245-	245-	245-	245-	245-			
135-	135-	135-	135-	135-	135-			
75-	75-	75-	75-	75-	75-			
48-	48-	48-	48-	48-	48-			
25-	25-	25-	25-	25-	25-			
11-	11-	11-	11-	11-	11-			
Target protein detected (arrowhead)	Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others	Target protein not detected	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein not captured in the IP	Target protein detected (white staining)	Target protein not detected	

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Figure 1: Rab13 antibody screening in western blot using an HEK-293T KO line

Figure 2: Rab13 antibody screening in western blot using siRNA in U-87 MG

Figure 3: Rab13 antibody screening in immunoprecipitation using U-87 MG lysates

Figure 4: Rab13 antibody screening in immunofluorescence using siRNA in U-87 MG

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Rab13 antibody screening in western blot using an HEK-293T KO line.

Lysates of HEK-293T WT and *RAB13* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Rab13 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of ctrl and KD lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab180936** at 1/200, ab205528** at 1/200, ab233810* at 1/1000, A10571 at 1/1000, MAB8305* at 1/200, 11718-1-AP at 1/500, 83336-2-RR** at 1/5000, MA5-31878* at 1/1000, MA5-31879* at 1/1000, MA5-37779* at 1/1000, and PA5-52039 at 1/1000. Antibodies ab180936**, ab205528**, and MAB8305* were titrated as the signal was too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. Predicted band size: 22.7 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: Rab13 antibody screening in western blot using siRNA in U87 MG

A) Lysates from DMS 53, HCT 116, BT-549, A-431, U-2 OS, U-87 MG, HT-1080, PANC-1, 5637, MDA-MB231, A549, and HeLa were prepared, and 20 µg of protein were processed in western blot with the Rab13 antibody PA5-52039 used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gel to the nitrocellulose membrane. Predicted band size: 22.7 kDa. **B)** Lysates of U-87 MG ctrl and *RAB13* KD were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Rab13 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of ctrl and KD lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab180936** at 1/200, ab205528** at 1/200, ab233810* at 1/1000, A10571 at 1/1000, MAB8305* at 1/200, 11718-1-AP at 1/500, 83336-2-RR** at 1/5000, MA5-31878* at 1/1000, MA5-31879* at 1/1000, MA5-37779* at 1/1000, and PA5-52039 at 1/1000. Antibodies ab180936**, ab205528**, and MAB8305* were titrated as the signal was too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. Predicted band size: 22.7 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: Rab13 antibody screening in immunoprecipitation using U-87 MG lysates.

U-87 MG lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated Rab13 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the Rab13 antibody 83336-2-RR** which was used at 1/5000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 4: Rab13 antibody screening in immunofluorescence using siRNA in U-87 MG.

U-87 MG ctrl and *RAB13* KD cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. Ctrl and KD cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on coverslips. Cells were stained with the indicated Rab13 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (ctrl), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KD) channels was performed. Representative images of the merged blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. Ctrl and KD cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: ab180936** at 1/600, ab205528** at 1/1000, ab233810* at 1/1000, A10571 at 1/100, MAB8305* at 1/500, 11718-1-AP at 1/1000, 83336-2-RR** at 1/200, MA5-31878* at 1/1000, MA5-31879* at 1/1000, MA5-37779* at 1/500, and PA5-52039 at 1/1000. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.